

Supplement of

Grounding line retreat and tide-modulated ocean channels at Moscow University and Totten Glacier ice shelves, East Antarctica

Tian Li et al.

Correspondence to: Tian Li (tian.li@bristol.ac.uk) and Jonathan L. Bamber (j.bamber@bristol.ac.uk)

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Figure S1. The ICESat-derived elevations (a) and elevation anomalies (b) along the RGT 323 at the main glacier trunk of the Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS) (c) processed in this study. The grey zones in (a) and (b) are the 1996 MEaSUREs DInSAR-derived ice shelf (Rignot et al., 2016, 2011). In subplots (a) and (b), the purple solid vertical lines are the Brunt et al. (2011) ICESat-derived Point F, the red dashed vertical lines are the manually picked Point F based on the elevation anomalies from repeat tracks L3A (June 21 – November 8, 2004) and L3D (June 23 – November 24, 2005) in (b). In (c), the data are overlaid on the Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica (Bindschadler et al., 2008).

Figure S2. The ice flowlines (white solid lines) used to measure the grounding line migrations between different time stamps at the main glacier trunks for Moscow University Ice Shelf (a) and the Totten Glacier Ice Shelf (b).

Figure S3. The ICESat-2-derived elevations (a) and elevation anomalies (b) along the track 163 GT2L across the Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS) southern subglacial lake (c). The grey zones in (a) and (b) are the subglacial lake boundary from 2018 Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR grounding line product (Mohajerani et al., 2021). In (c), the data are overlaid on the Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica (Bindschadler et al., 2008). The ICESat-2 data used in detecting subglacial lake is version 5 between 30 March 2019 and 22 December 2021.

Figure S4. The ICESat-2-derived elevations (a) and elevation anomalies (b) along the track 338 GT2R across the Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS) southern subglacial lake (c). The grey zones in (a) and (b) are the subglacial lake boundary from 2018 Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR grounding line product (Mohajerani et al., 2021). In (c), the data are overlaid on the Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica (Bindschadler et al., 2008). The ICESat-2 data used in detecting subglacial lake is version 5 between 30 March 2019 and 22 December 2021.

Figure S5. The ICESat-2-derived elevations (a) and elevation anomalies (b) along the track 605 GT3L across the Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS) northern subglacial lake (c). The grey zones in (a) and (b) are the subglacial lake boundary from Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR grounding line on 8 September 2021 mapped in this study (Figure 2g). In (c), the data are overlaid on the Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica (Bindschadler et al., 2008). The ICESat-2 data used in detecting subglacial lake is version 5 between 30 March 2019 and 22 December 2021.

Figure S6. Height above hydrostatic equilibrium at the two subglacial lakes near Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS) main glacier trunk mapped in this study (Figure 2).

Figure S7. The spatial distributions of the CATS2008 reference points (circles) and FES2014 references points (triangles) used in the DInSAR tidal amplitude predictions for each studied region. Note FES2014 tidal model does not provide tidal predictions over the ice shelves, its tidal prediction reference points are located off coast.

Figure S8. The repeat track analysis of ICESat-2 elevation profiles on the Totten Glacier Ice Shelf (TGIS) main glacier trunk along track 1207 GT2R (a), track 1207 GT3L (b), track 1032 GT1L (c) and track 1032 GT2R (d), respectively.

Figure S9. BedMachine bed elevation (Morphing et al., 2020) overlaid with different grounding zone products. The ESA CCI DInSAR grounding lines in 1996 are shown as the yellow solid lines in all subplots (ESA, 2017).

Table S1. Modelled tidal amplitudes and grounding line (GL) retreat compared with 1996 MEaSUREs GL for Sentinel-1a/b interferograms at Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS) main glacier trunk (Fig. 2b). Each row represents a different interferogram generated from three different Sentinel-1 image scenes acquired at time stamps of t_1 , t_2 and t_3 . The nominal time stamp of each interferogram is t_2 . h_1 , h_2 and h_3 are the tidal amplitude predictions at each acquisition date calculated from CATS2008 (Padman et al., 2002) and FES2014 tidal models (Lyard et al., 2021). The tidal prediction reference points are shown in Figure S7. The tidal amplitudes are used to identify $h_{\max}$, the highest positive tides among all different tides ($h_{\max} = \max(h_1, h_2, h_3)$) (Brancato et al., 2020). The differential tidal prediction δh from the tidal models for each Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR interferogram is calculated as $\delta h = (h_3 - h_2) - (h_2 - h_1)$.

Time stamp of SAR pass 1 (t_1)	Time stamp of SAR pass 2 (t_2)	Time stamp of SAR pass 3 (t_3)	Modelled tide amplitude of h_1 at t_1 (cm)	Modelled tide amplitude of h_2 at t_2 (cm)	Modelled tide amplitude of h_3 at t_3 (cm)	$h_{\max}$ (cm)	δh (cm)	GL retreat since 1996 along ice flowline in Figure 2 (km)
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CATS2008 Tide Model (-67.0714°S, 120.6249°E)								
20210417T121114	20210423T121156	20210429T121114	-27.95	34.80	-80.60	34.80	-178.15	3.14 ± 0.13
20210423T121156	20210429T121114	20210505T121156	34.80	-80.60	32.45	34.80	228.45	5.67 ± 0.13
20210429T121114	20210505T121156	20210511T121115	-80.60	32.45	-50.80	32.45	-196.30	3.84 ± 0.13
FES2014 Tide Model (-66.3102°S, 122.6998°E)								
20210417T121114	20210423T121156	20210429T121114	-28.71	35.42	-75.53	35.42	-175.08	3.14 ± 0.13
20210423T121156	20210429T121114	20210505T121156	35.42	-75.53	33.79	35.42	220.28	5.67 ± 0.13
20210429T121114	20210505T121156	20210511T121115	-75.53	33.79	-44.66	33.79	-187.78	3.84 ± 0.13

Table S2. The acquisition time of ERS-1/2 SAR images used in 1996 MEaSURES DInSAR grounding line mapping and the corresponding modelled tidal amplitudes calculated from CATS2008 (Padman et al., 2002) and FES2014 tidal models (Lyard et al., 2021) on the Moscow University Western Ice Shelf (MUWIS), Moscow University Ice Shelf (MUIS), Totten Glacier Eastern Ice Shelf (TGEIS), Totten Glacier Ice Shelf (TGIS) and Totten Glacier Eastern Branch (TGEB). The differential tidal predictions δh at four satellite passes used in DInSAR interferogram mapping is calculated as $\delta h = (h_4 - h_3) - (h_2 - h_1)$ where h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4 are the modelled tidal amplitudes at each time stamp (Fricker et al., 2009).

Time of SAR pass	Latitude	Longitude	CATS2008 tide amplitude (cm)	FES2014 tide amplitude (cm)	CATS2008 δh (cm)	FES2014 δh (cm)	CATS2 008 $ \delta h $ (cm)	FES2 014 $ \delta h $ (cm)
MUWIS & MUIS								
19960214T003648	-66.3102	122.6998	-34.51	-38.25				
19960215T003651	-66.3102	122.6998	-31.01	-35.28	-11.22	-10.76	11.22	10.76
19960320T003651	-66.3102	122.6998	-18.79	-21.90				
19960321T003650	-66.3102	122.6998	-26.51	-29.69				
TGEIS								
19960310T005108	-66.9212	117.2723	-44.66	-47.27				
19960311T005107	-66.9212	117.2723	-45.44	-47.68	8.60	9.77	8.60	9.77
19960414T005110	-66.9212	117.2723	3.71	2.00				
19960415T005109	-66.9212	117.2723	11.53	11.36				
TGIS								
19960313T005654	-66.6687	116.4448	-38.60	-41.91				
19960314T005700	-66.6687	116.4448	-31.45	-36.09	-15.24	-14.53	15.24	14.53
19960417T005658	-66.6687	116.4448	10.08	10.92				
19960418T005712	-66.6687	116.4448	1.99	2.21				
TGEB								
19960313T005654	-66.6687	116.4448	-38.60	-41.91				
19960314T005659	-66.6687	116.4448	-31.45	-36.09	-15.35	-14.64	15.35	14.64
19960417T005658	-66.6687	116.4448	10.08	10.92				
19960418T005657	-66.6687	116.4448	1.89	2.10				

Table S3. The grounding line migration between ICESat-2-derived Point F and MEaSURES 1996 DInSAR grounding line (GL) along the ice flowlines shown in Figure S2a on the Moscow University Ice Shelf. The tidal ranges are derived from the ICESat-2 elevation anomaly profiles. The time stamp of ICESat-2-derived Point F is defined as year 2020.

Moscow University Ice Shelf

Track number	GL retreat 1996 - 2020 (km)	GL retreat rate 1996 - 2020 (km yr ⁻¹)	Tidal range (m)	Ice velocity at Point F (m yr ⁻¹)	Repeat cycles
Western flank					
841-1-l	13.79 ± 0.1	0.57	0.89	337.5	5, 7
841-1-r	13.91 ± 0.1	0.58	0.94	337.5	5, 7
Eastern flank					
1108-2-l	10.95 ± 0.1	0.46	0.55	336.2	6, 7
1108-2-r	11.13 ± 0.1	0.46	0.54	336.2	6, 7
1283-1-r	8.71 ± 0.1	0.36	0.65	330.2	4, 5
1108-3-pair	8.70 ± 0.1	0.36	0.23	329.6	6, 7
1108-3-r	8.62 ± 0.1	0.36	0.49	329.6	6, 7
1108-3-l	8.89 ± 0.1	0.37	0.27	330.2	6, 7
1283-1-pair	9.03 ± 0.1	0.38	0.61	335.1	4, 5
1283-1-l	8.93 ± 0.1	0.37	0.61	335.1	4, 5

Table S4. The grounding line migration between ICESat-2-derived Point F and MEaSURES 1996 DInSAR-derived GL along the ice flowlines shown in Figure S2b at the main glacier trunk of Totten Glacier Ice Shelf (TGIS). The tidal ranges are derived from the ICESat-2 elevation anomalies at Point H. The time stamp of ICESat-2-derived Point F is defined as year 2020.

Totten Glacier Ice Shelf							
Track number	GL retreat 1996 - 2013 (km)	GL retreat 2013 - 2020 (km)	GL retreat rate 2013 - 2020 (km yr ⁻¹)	GL retreat rate 1996 - 2013 (km yr ⁻¹)	Tidal Range (m)	Ice velocity at Point F (m yr ⁻¹)	Repeat cycles
1207-3-l	2.08 ± 0.1	1.64 ± 0.1	0.23	0.12	2.85	828.8	4, 5, 8
1032-1-r	1.97 ± 0.1	2.08 ± 0.1	0.30	0.12	4.89	820.7	4, 8, 9
1032-1-l	1.93 ± 0.1	2.33 ± 0.1	0.33	0.11	4.86	811.7	4, 8, 9
1032-1-pair	1.93 ± 0.1	2.27 ± 0.1	0.32	0.11	4.91	811.7	4, 8, 9
1207-2-r	2.17 ± 0.1	1.45 ± 0.1	0.21	0.13	1.98	805.2	4, 5, 8
1207-2-pair	2.16 ± 0.1	1.41 ± 0.1	0.20	0.13	2.11	805.2	4, 5, 8
1032-2-l	2.04 ± 0.1	1.37 ± 0.1	0.20	0.12	3.86	753.9	3,4,8,9,10
1032-2-pair	2.03 ± 0.1	1.38 ± 0.1	0.20	0.12	3.96	753.9	3,4,8,9,10
1032-2-r	2.02 ± 0.1	1.40 ± 0.1	0.20	0.12	3.92	753.9	3,4,8,9,10
1207-1-r	2.03 ± 0.1	0.81 ± 0.1	0.12	0.12	0.83	715.8	4, 5
1207-1-l	2.05 ± 0.1	0.77 ± 0.1	0.11	0.12	1.06	715.8	4, 5
1207-1-pair	2.04 ± 0.1	0.75 ± 0.1	0.11	0.12	1.09	715.8	4, 5

Table S5. Modelled tidal amplitudes and grounding line (GL) retreat compared with 1996 MEaSURES GL for Sentinel-1a/b interferograms at the Totten Glacier East Branch (TGEB) ice stream (Fig. 6). Each row represents a different interferogram generated from three different Sentinel-1 image scenes acquired at time stamps of t1, t2 and t3. The nominal time stamp of each interferogram is t2. h1, h2 and h3 are the tidal amplitude predictions at each acquisition date calculated from CATS2008 (Padman et al., 2002) and FES2014 tidal models (Lyard et al., 2021). The tidal prediction reference points are shown in Figure S7. The tidal amplitudes are used to identify $h_{\max}$, the highest tidal amplitude ($h_{\max} = \max(h_1, h_2, h_3)$) (Brancato et al., 2020). The differential tidal prediction δh from the tidal models for each Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR interferogram is calculated as $\delta h = (h_3 - h_2) - (h_2 - h_1)$.

Time stamp of SAR pass 1 (t1)	Time stamp of SAR pass 2 (t2)	Time stamp of SAR pass 3 (t3)	Modelled tide amplitude de h1 at t1 (cm)	Modelled tide amplitude de h2 at t2 (cm)	Modelled tide amplitude de h3 at t3 (cm)	$h_{\max}$ (cm)	δh (cm)	GL retreat since 1996 along ice flowline in Figure 6 (km)
CATS2008 Tidal Model (-67.0043°S, 115.8222°E)								
20180301T123555	20180307T123513	20180313T123556	-2.64	-23.07	34.82	34.82	78.31	5.15 ± 0.13
20190119T123603	20190125T123521	20190131T123602	62.07	-51.09	50.53	62.07	214.77	4.84 ± 0.13
20190302T123520	20190308T123602	20190314T123520	40.04	-47.65	12.88	40.04	148.21	6.57 ± 0.13
20190308T123602	20190314T123520	20190320T123602	-47.65	12.88	-14.5	12.88	-87.9	6.45 ± 0.13
20190507T123603	20190513T123522	20190519T123604	-67.43	31.79	-67.92	31.79	-198.93	6.96 ± 0.13
20200308T123526	20200314T123608	20200320T123527	21.77	-36.85	32.65	32.65	128.13	4.64 ± 0.13
20200401T123527	20200407T123609	20200413T123527	15.07	-28.61	-9.58	15.07	62.71	6.76 ± 0.13
20200718T123532	20200724T123615	20200730T123533	-40	-47	-29.78	-29.78	24.23	6.06 ± 0.13
20210309T123614	20210315T123532	20210321T123614	54.46	-57.46	11.93	54.46	181.31	6.4 ± 0.13
20210402T123614	20210408T123533	20210414T123615	-35.04	22.07	-62.81	22.07	-141.99	5.58 ± 0.13
20210420T123533	20210426T123615	20210502T123534	17.55	-42.46	-3.08	17.55	99.37	6 ± 0.13
FES2014 Tidal Model (-66.6687°S, 116.4448°E)								
20180301T123555	20180307T123513	20180313T123556	3.42	-20.85	38.46	38.46	83.58	5.15 ± 0.13
20190119T123603	20190125T123521	20190131T123602	66.61	-48.72	55.54	66.61	219.59	4.84 ± 0.13
20190302T123520	20190308T123602	20190314T123520	43.98	-43.14	15.77	43.98	146.04	6.57 ± 0.13
20190308T123602	20190314T123520	20190320T123602	-43.14	15.77	-7.77	15.77	-82.46	6.45 ± 0.13
20190507T123603	20190513T123522	20190519T123604	-65.6	32.93	-66.61	32.93	-198.06	6.96 ± 0.13
20200308T123526	20200314T123608	20200320T123527	28.23	-34.34	36.6	36.6	133.52	4.64 ± 0.13
20200401T123527	20200407T123609	20200413T123527	17.94	-23.34	-7.06	17.94	57.57	6.76 ± 0.13
20200718T123532	20200724T123615	20200730T123533	-42.74	-47.63	-31.76	-31.76	20.77	6.06 ± 0.13
20210309T123614	20210315T123532	20210321T123614	60.17	-52.41	13.72	60.17	178.71	6.4 ± 0.13
20210402T123614	20210408T123533	20210414T123615	-32.04	27.58	-58.51	27.58	-145.71	5.58 ± 0.13
20210420T123533	20210426T123615	20210502T123534	21.23	-38.59	-0.27	21.23	98.14	6 ± 0.13

Table S6. Modelled tidal amplitudes and grounding line (GL) retreat compared with 1996 MEaSURES GL for Sentinel-1a/b interferograms at the Moscow University Western Ice Shelf (MUWIS) ocean channel (Fig. 8). Each row represents a different interferogram generated from three different Sentinel-1 image scenes acquired at time stamps of t1, t2 and t3. The nominal time stamp of each interferogram is t2. h1, h2 and h3 are the tidal amplitude predictions at each acquisition date calculated from CATS2008 (Padman et al., 2002) and FES2014 tidal models (Lyard et al., 2021). The tidal prediction reference points are shown in Figure S7. The tidal amplitudes are used to identify $h_{\max}$, the highest tidal amplitude ($h_{\max} = \max(h_1, h_2, h_3)$) (Brancato et al., 2020). The absolute differential tidal prediction $|\delta h|$ from the tidal models for each Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR interferogram is calculated as $|\delta h| = |(h_3 - h_2) - (h_2 - h_1)|$.

Time stamp of SAR pass 1 (t1)	Time stamp of SAR pass 2 (t2)	Time stamp of SAR pass 3 (t3)	Modelled tide amplitude de h1 at t1 (cm)	Modelled tide amplitude de h2 at t2 (cm)	Modelled tide amplitude de h3 at t3 (cm)	$h_{\max}$ (cm)	$ \delta h $ (cm)	Channel width (m)
CATS2008 Tidal Model (-67.0407°S, 118.756°E)								
20180304T121054	20180310T121136	20180316T121054	-61.26	29.14	-10.02	29.14	129.56	3128 ± 127
20180322T121136	20180328T121054	20180403T121136	-35.4	34.74	-58.13	34.74	163.01	1442 ± 127
20200305T121107	20200311T121149	20200317T121107	56.74	-71.91	43.07	56.74	243.63	2666 ± 127
20210411T121155	20210417T121114	20210423T121156	-38.12	-24.39	32.52	32.52	43.18	0
20210417T121114	20210423T121156	20210429T121114	-24.39	32.52	-77.55	32.52	166.98	2187 ± 127
20210423T121156	20210429T121114	20210505T121156	32.52	-77.55	32.11	32.52	219.73	2837 ± 127
20210429T121114	20210505T121156	20210511T121115	-77.55	32.11	-51.67	32.11	193.44	1621 ± 127
FES2014 Tidal Model (-66.8536°S, 119.1516°E)								
20180304T121054	20180310T121136	20180316T121054	-60.57	30.05	-7.39	30.05	128.07	3128 ± 127
20180322T121136	20180328T121054	20180403T121136	-33.99	39.37	-57.17	39.37	169.9	1442 ± 127
20200305T121107	20200311T121149	20200317T121107	58.87	-70	47.38	58.87	246.25	2666 ± 127
20210411T121155	20210417T121114	20210423T121156	-35.19	-25.68	35.3	35.3	51.47	0

20210417T121114	20210423T121156	20210429T121114	-25.68	35.3	-76.7	35.3	172.98	2187 ± 127
20210423T121156	20210429T121114	20210505T121156	35.3	-76.7	36.87	36.87	225.57	2837 ± 127
20210429T121114	20210505T121156	20210511T121115	-76.7	36.87	-48.76	36.87	199.2	1621 ± 127

Table S7. Modelled tidal amplitudes and grounding line (GL) retreat compared with 1996 MEaSURES GL for Sentinel-1a/b interferograms at the Totten Glacier Eastern Ice Shelf (TGEIS) ocean channel (Fig. 9). Each row represents a different interferogram generated from three different Sentinel-1 image scenes acquired at time stamps of t1, t2 and t3. The nominal time stamp of each interferogram is t2. h1, h2 and h3 are the tidal amplitude predictions at each acquisition date calculated from CATS2008 (Padman et al., 2002) and FES2014 tidal models (Lyard et al., 2021). The tidal prediction reference points are shown in Figure S7. The tidal amplitudes are used to identify h_{max} , the highest tidal amplitude ($h_{max}=\max(h_1, h_2, h_3)$) (Brancato et al., 2020). The absolute differential tidal prediction $|\delta h|$ from the tidal models for each Sentinel-1a/b DInSAR interferogram are calculated as $|\delta h| = |(h_3 - h_2) - (h_2 - h_1)|$.

Time stamp of SAR pass 1 (t1)	Time stamp of SAR pass 2 (t2)	Time stamp of SAR pass 3 (t3)	Modelle d tide amplitu de h1 at t1 (cm)	Modelle d tide amplitu de h2 at t2 (cm)	Modelle d tide amplitu de h3 at t3 (cm)	h_{max} (cm)	$ \delta h $ (cm)	Channel width (m)
CATS2008 Tidal Model (-67.0131°S, 117.0389°E)								
20170818T121137	20170824T121056	20170830T121138	-30.65	-49.05	-24.28	-24.28	43.16	0
20171101T123559	20171107T123517	20171113T123558	12.19	-36.40	10.85	12.19	95.83	2950 ± 127
20180304T121054	20180310T121136	20180316T121054	-62.85	29.88	-12.60	29.88	135.20	3858 ± 127
20180310T121136	20180316T121054	20180322T121136	29.88	-12.60	-34.79	29.88	20.29	0
20180322T121136	20180328T121054	20180403T121136	-34.79	33.19	-59.05	33.19	160.22	1814 ± 127
20190305T121142	20190311T121101	20190317T121142	-5.50	-39.57	58.67	58.67	132.31	1749 ± 127
20190311T121101	20190317T121142	20190323T121101	-39.57	58.67	-73.56	58.67	230.47	3505 ± 127
20190317T121142	20190323T121101	20190329T121143	58.67	-73.56	34.32	58.67	240.10	3893 ± 127
20200715T121113	20200721T121155	20200727T121113	-16.48	-59.61	-16.65	-16.48	86.09	0
20200727T121113	20200802T121156	20200808T121114	-16.65	-51.45	-31.80	-16.65	54.45	1236 ± 127
20200814T121156	20200820T121115	20200826T121157	-30.25	-56.06	-32.94	-30.25	48.92	1516 ± 127
20210411T121155	20210417T121114	20210423T121156	-40.75	-24.00	31.79	31.79	39.04	0
20210417T121114	20210423T121156	20210429T121114	-24.00	31.79	-78.84	31.79	166.41	2613 ± 127
20210423T121156	20210429T121114	20210505T121156	31.79	-78.84	32.39	32.39	221.86	2887 ± 127
FES2014 Tidal Model (-66.9212°S, 117.2723°E)								
20170818T121137	20170824T121056	20170830T121138	-34.18	-51.70	-27.03	-27.03	42.19	0
20171101T123559	20171107T123517	20171113T123558	10.35	-35.61	12.57	12.57	94.14	2950 ± 127
20180304T121054	20180310T121136	20180316T121054	-61.90	31.06	-9.95	31.06	133.97	3858 ± 127
20180310T121136	20180316T121054	20180322T121136	31.06	-9.95	-32.80	31.06	18.16	0
20180322T121136	20180328T121054	20180403T121136	-32.80	38.00	-57.80	38.00	166.60	1814 ± 127
20190305T121142	20190311T121101	20190317T121142	-2.51	-39.54	62.50	62.50	139.07	1749 ± 127
20190311T121101	20190317T121142	20190323T121101	-39.54	62.50	-72.47	62.50	237.01	3505 ± 127
20190317T121142	20190323T121101	20190329T121143	62.50	-72.47	36.94	62.50	244.38	3893 ± 127
20200715T121113	20200721T121155	20200727T121113	-16.49	-59.69	-17.72	-16.49	85.17	0
20200727T121113	20200802T121156	20200808T121114	-17.72	-53.95	-33.99	-17.72	56.20	1236 ± 127
20200814T121156	20200820T121115	20200826T121157	-33.30	-56.60	-34.18	-33.30	45.73	1516 ± 127
20210411T121155	20210417T121114	20210423T121156	-37.74	-24.78	34.70	34.70	46.51	0
20210417T121114	20210423T121156	20210429T121114	-24.78	34.70	-77.50	34.70	171.67	2613 ± 127
20210423T121156	20210429T121114	20210505T121156	34.70	-77.50	37.39	37.39	227.08	2887 ± 127

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